

OFFSET FAILURE IN FILLED HOLE COMPRESSION TESTS

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1 Introduction

Filled hole compression tests are usually conducted in the purpose for determining allowables (r_0 and d_0) which are necessary for the application of point-stress method [1]. These tests are very common and are made in the scheme of the pyramid of test [2] described in the US Military Handbook or in [3]. Classical failure modes are also described in the US Military Handbook [2] and several studies (for example [4,5]). Most studies focus on the modelling and experimental identification of damage in fastened joints or pinned hole [6,7], and on the influence of design: clearance, tightening effect or washer effects [8–12]. It is noticeable that most studies deal with single or double lap joint. Less attention was dedicated to Filled Hole Tension (FHT) [13] or Compression (FHC) tests [14]. In the last case a particular failure mode may occur and is reported by [2] and was observed in [15,16]: the laminate off-set compression failure (see also Fig. 1). In the US- Mil Hbk, this failure was attributed to bearing bypass loads. In this experimental study, this mode was also observed by classical post-mortem analysis but further investigation were conducted using high-speed cameras to capture the failure scenario which is not related in our experiments to bearing loads.

2 Specimen and test description

A plate is manufactured by manually laying up unidirectional plies of pre-impregnated carbon laminate (intermediary modulus and epoxy resin).

After curing, the specimens are cut out following different orientations (see Fig. 2). In the X-axis, the stacking includes 10 plies at 0° , 4 plies at 45° , 4 plies at 135° and 2 plies at 90° . The stacking

sequence is $[0_2, 45, 90, -45, 0, 45, 0, -45, 0]_s$. This lay-up is referred to $[10/4/4/2]$ in the following.

In the Y-axis, the stacking sequence is thus $[2/4/4/10]$. The specimen is designed according to the European standard of holed composite specimen for compressive load tests (DIN EN ISO 14126). The thickness of the specimen is about 5 mm and the dimensions of the specimen are 32 mm wide and 142 mm long. Fibre glass reinforcement of 55 mm long are bonded on the both sides of the specimens (see Figure N° 3). A 6.35 mm hole is drilled at the centre of the specimens.

Fig. 1: Laminate Offset Failure.

Three effects are studied:

* Torque/lateral constraint: some specimens were tested with bolt but no nut, some with finger tight torque.

* Bolt material: Titanium or Steel.

* Lay-up/off axis: 0° ([10/4/4/2]), 90° ([2/4/4/10]) and off-axis: 22.5° , 45° , 67.5° (Figure N° 2). All the off-axis specimens hold a titanium bolt with finger tight torque.

Fig. 2: Cutting of specimens in the plate.

For each configuration, three tests are carried out to get an evaluation of the scattering. A total of 39 specimens are tested. The test set-up is showed Fig. 4a. A 160 kN compression test machine is used with hydraulic grips. The load cell of the machine provides the compression force and the loading rate is 1 mm/mn. A high-speed camera (set at 10,000 pictures/s) is necessary to capture the damage scenario (Fig. 4b). The use of cold light spotlights is required because the temperature of the specimen increases quickly with classical spotlight.

Even with this apparatus, a ventilator and a thermocouple are installed to monitor properly the temperature of the specimen (see principle Fig. 5). As the frequency of the high-speed camera is very short (a sliding window of several seconds), digital camcorder are also used and installed on both side of the specimen to capture slow events. Moreover, for several tests, after observing material ejection phenomenom, two mirrors were installed on the side of the specimen and oriented at 45° (see Fig. 5). It was thus possible to analyse the events which occurs trough the thickness of the edges of the specimens.

Fig. 3: Specimens sample.

Fig. 4: General view of tests equipment.

Fig. 5: Test set-up principle.

3 Results

The strain gauges measurement are not provided here since the response is quasi linear until failure. Only parasitic bending moments were identified due to a small curvature of the specimens. The failure loads without scatter bars are given Fig. 6 a,b. The values are the average of the three tests carried out for each configuration and are normalized by respect to each maximum fixed to 100.

The following remarks can be highlighted:

- Filled hole effect: the failure load decreases between the reference and the drilled specimens for the [10/4/4/2] stacking but remain almost the same for [2/4/4/10] stacking. (42 for the reference, between 39 and 42 with bolts).
- Bolt material effect: for [2/4/4/10] stacking, it is not possible to identify a clear trend on the influence of bolt material because the differences are about 5% and hidden by the scatter. However, this result is consistent with the flexibility of this stacking. For stacking [10/4/4/2], the sensitivity to the bolt material seems to be more important especially for the tightened specimens.

Fig. 6: Failure loads for Filled Hole Compression tests .

- Lateral constraint effect: for [2/4/4/10] stacking, it is not possible to identify a clear trend because the differences are about 5% and hidden by the scatter. For [10/4/4/2] stacking, the normalized load for a tightened titanium bolt is 86 and decrease to 76 for a non tightened specimen, i.e. -12%. This result is in opposition with the literature. Usually, tightening a bolt has a positive effect by containment of the bearing or by the effect of transverse compressive stresses on the delamination onset. For the steel bolt, it is not possible to conclude because the scatter is too high

To understand this behavior, a classical post-mortem analysis was first performed. Sample of failures patterns for [10/4/4/2] specimens are shown in Fig. 7 (tightened bolt) and Fig. 8 (no lateral constraint).

Several failure modes are superimposed with net section compression failure and cleavage. On the edges of the specimens, delaminations are also observed. Generally speaking, the pattern is different between the kind of specimen and one can assume that the failure scenario is different. Sample of failures patterns for [2/4/4/10] specimens are shown Fig. 9 and Fig. 10. Unlike the previous tests, it is not necessary to make a difference between tightened or not specimens. For all the specimens, fracture lines are clearly visible in the net section (Fig. 10) or in off-set sections (Fig. 9).

Nevertheless, for tightened specimens the fracture line is always tangent to the bolt. On the edges of the specimens, delaminations are also visible (Specimen C, Fig. 11). The different fracture line patterns are summarized in Fig. 12. The fracture lines follow the main direction of the axis and are not located in the net section. For this original failure pattern, one can speak of “generalized off-set failure”.

This classical post-mortem analysis shows that for all the specimens cracks appears in the net or in off-set sections and seems to be the main failure mode. In order to better understand the failure scenarios, a more advanced experimental analysis was carried out by using high speed camera.

Fig. 8: Post-mortem failure patterns of [10/4/4/2] specimens with no lateral constraint.

Fig. 7: Post-mortem failure patterns of [10/4/4/2] specimens with tightened bolts.

Fig. 9: Post-mortem failure patterns of [2/4/4/10] specimens (D = 4.8 mm).

Fig. 10: Post-mortem failure patterns of [2/4/4/10] specimens (D = 6.35 mm).

Fig. 11: Side view of failure patterns of a [2/4/4/10] specimens (D = 6.35 mm) with a tightened bolt.

Fig. 12: Fracture Location

4 High speed camera analysis: identification of the failure scenario

When tested, all the specimen failed in an explosive way and no difference could be visually observed. However, using high speed camera, different failure sequences and speeds were recorded: from 1/100th to 1/10000th s. The three pictures of Fig. 13 shows the failure sequence in a [10/4/4/2] specimen with a tightened bolt.

Fig. 13: Failure of a [10/4/4/2] specimen with a tightened bolt.

The crack initiates at the periphery of the bolt for all the specimens with a little off-set from the net section. It then propagates relatively slowly (within several 1/1000th s) to the edge of the specimen.

The three pictures of Fig. 14 shows the crack propagation of a [10/4/4/2] specimen with no lateral constraint. The crack initiates in the net section near the bolt and propagates in an explosive way. Therefore, the three pictures were taken every 1/10000th s.

For both cases, the final failure mode is a static failure of the upper ply oriented at 0°. However, the presence of the nut has an effect on the location of the initiation of the crack. As the failure seems to be a pure static failure, the bearing stresses and the delaminations may not have any influence. So the tightening modifies the local triaxial stress concentration and load transfer between the hole and the bolt and can explain the difference observed in the failure loads between the specimens. However, this assumption is still to be demonstrated by a numerical analysis.

Fig. 14: Failure of a [10/4/4/2] specimen with no lateral constraint.

In the sequence of pictures 1 to 4 given Fig. 15, a phenomenon of material ejection is showed. It is localized in the edge of a [2/4/4/10] stacking specimen. This phenomenon was observed only for this stacking and for all the configuration of bolts.

The location of the ejection was never in the net section. It occurs prior to any apparent damage and nothing was detected on the load/displacement curves. After this observation, in order to identify the mechanisms, some mirrors were installed as described Fig. 5.

In the sequence of pictures given, the failure scenario for [2/4/4/10] specimen is showed Fig. 16. Thanks to the mirror, the apparition of a delamination in the edge can be observed (Step 1). Clearly, interlaminar normal and shear stresses occurring in the region near the free edge due to high stress gradients can cause this delamination [15]. Moreover, this observation is consistent with the previous phenomenon of material ejection which seems to correspond to the onset of delamination (Fig. 15). Afterwards, the delamination propagates relatively slowly (Step 2). The sequence takes about 1/100th s. When the delamination area is large enough, a local buckling of the upper plies occurs (Step 3), and a net failure at the tip of the wave happens immediately (Step 3).

It is this fracture line which can be observed in the post-mortem pattern (Figs. 9 and 10). This scenario explains the fact that due to a tightened bold, the buckling wave is always located at the same place. Thus, the stress concentration occurs at the periphery of the bolt and the fracture line initiates only at this place.

Fig. 14: Material ejection phenomenon of [2/4/4/10] stacking specimen.

For specimens with no lateral constraint, the wave depends on the delamination which initiates randomly along the edge of the specimen. Thus the tip of the wave can be located anywhere, even in the net section as described Fig. 10. So for this configuration, the off-set failures cannot be attributed to bearing by-pass failures, as in reference [2]. The off-set failures are due to a specimen effect.

Fig. 15: Failure scenario for [2/4/4/10] stacking specimens.

It is noticeable that the same scenario was identified for off-axis specimens. A delamination initiates in the edges of the specimens and a local buckling occurs afterwards generating off-axis and offset splitting [16].

4 Conclusions

An advanced experimental study was conducted on Filled Hole Compression test of carbon/epoxy specimens. For the configurations analysed, net compression failures were observed for [10/4/4/2] stacking. It was due to stress concentration that located at the periphery of the bolt or the drilled hole. For [2/4/4/10] and off-axis stackings [, off-set 16] failures were identified. These failures were not due to bearing stresses but to an edge delamination, followed by a local buckling. The results obtained in this study are the basis for developing more robust sizing methods for bolted joints based on physical understanding of failure mechanism and associated sensitivity parameters. More specifically, the results obtained (specimen edge effects) invalidate the classical point-stress method for some cases.

Moreover, this failure on a simple specimen demonstrates the complexity of the failure scenario of composite structures and the need of refined experimental investigation to identify it. The next step of the analysis is to capture these failure scenarios by finite element modeling. Preliminary results show that Discrete Ply Method is efficient [17, 18].

5. References

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